

Second edition

First edition will be written first followed by the second edition

The first edition

Subject: Mathematical Scientific Paper/ Proposal “hasn’t been published yet”.

Scope: Abstract Algebra and Quantum field theory.

Achieved Result to discuss: Complete model to describe a mathematical universe.

To whom it may concern.

Dear Respectful Professor,

It gives me great pleasure to discuss/ present a different and unique perspective to describe a complete model for a mathematical universe.

I have an abiding, passionate and almost obsessive interest in mathematics that began since I have been researching diligently for more than 15 years of self-research, tracing the trail of previous mathematicians, and tracking the history of mathematics and physics.

Beyond my research considering quaternions and Hurwitz primes, I have reached to amazing results: “as a subring of quaternions with some properties defined on it, can amazingly work as a model to describe a mathematical universe where a distribution of matter on three-dimension space changing as the real part of a quaternion number changes capturing the universe as one wave and quantum leap and maximum speed. And the most important is not knowing where we are in that ring captures exactly the universe as a wave of probability collapsing to smaller probability moment after moment”.

Hence, I wish I will be given an opportunity to demonstrate my value as a researcher. The ability to devote my life to pursuing mathematical research and imparting my knowledge is simply a dream comes true. I would be honored to have a chance for scientific discussion.

I’m looking forward to having an opportunity to move forward through further details in depth.

Thank you deeply for your kindness and attention.

Sincerely,

Amgad Ahmed, Researcher

GRE Math 2021

The second edition

More details are written in this edition

The idea is to construct a function from the set of quaternion integers to the set of 1 and 0.

The output is 1 if the quaternion is prime (irreducible quaternion) and 0 if the quaternion is not prime (reducible quaternion).

A representation of this function is an infinite dimensions tensor of rank 4.

This tensor is going to be our description for a quantum field in a mathematical universe (may captures some properties of the real universe) as follow:

First and most important we keep the tensor with its outputs zeros and ones and imagine going to somewhere in this infinite dimension tensor of rank 4 and erase any data telling us where we are in the tensor.

Again, we don't have any data telling us where we are but we have the tensor with its output's zeros and ones.

(Important note: some others quantum fields could be constructed. Examples: for each quaternion number which consists of four numbers, if tow numbers of them are relatively primes then the output is 1 otherwise the output is zero. What if three are relatively prime? what if one is prime? It's clear that one can construct a lot of these quantum fields).

(One more important note: the outputs will be later finite dimensions vectors consisting of ones and zeroes components. simply speaking, we combine n functions together from the set of quaternion integers to the set of n dimensions vectors of ones and zeros components. Then the representation of this n functions will be an infinite dimensions tensor of rank 4 with its outputs n dimensions vectors with components ones and zeros. This will allow us later to capture n quantum fields interacting together. but for simplicity we will start by only one quantum field.).

Now we will consider this infinite dimension of rank 4 tensor with outputs zeros and ones as a universe. We can imagine that we are somewhere in this tensor and we don't know where we are but we can observe these ones and zeroes in some parts of it (we can imagine that some parts are measured where we can observe these ones and zeros but some other parts are still not measured (where the outputs are still unknown))

Now using our knowledge about prime numbers distribution, even if we don't know where we are in this tensor, measuring some parts of this tensor enable us to get probability distributions of the unmeasured parts. moreover, the more we measure, the more theses probability distributions collapse.

The conclusion is that this tensor captures a mathematical universe, 4 dimensions spacetime, one is different than the other three, three for space and one for time. quantum length and period.

Quantum fields interacting together, and most important captures the universe as one wave of probability collapsing to smaller probabilities as we do the act of observation.